

THE INFLUENCE OF KNOWLEDGE, SKILL AND MOTIVATION TOWARDS JOB PERFORMANCE AMONG YOUNG EXECUTIVE OFFICERS IN ROYAL MALAYSIAN NAVY

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ABSTRACT

The objectives of the study are to investigate the influence of knowledge, communication skill and motivation toward job performance among the Young Executive Officer in Royal Malaysian Navy (RMN). The issues about safety of the ship at sea has become main concern in RMN. A lot of incident involving collision between Naval ship all around the world with merchant ship has cause the RMN to be more cautious and stringent in handling and navigating the ship especially when operating in busiest straits like Singapore Strait. Thus, the performance of each officer must be determined to ensure their capability in handling and navigate the ship. The study covers the factors that affected performance of young officers on board warship which related to the training program undergo by Young Executive Officers before served on board ship. The study used the Campbell Theory and the respondents consists of 127 Young Executive Officers from naval base in Perak, Malaysia. The online questionnaires were used in this study and analyzed by using Statistical Packages for Social Science (SPSS). Research findings show that there is a significant influence between specialization knowledge and motivation toward job performance among Young Executive Officer. However, knowledge in information processing, specialization knowledge and communication skill have no significant influence toward job performance. Based on the result, there are several recommendations such as establishing pre-joining program and design specific program for confident level to enhance the performance of young executive officer.

Keywords: knowledge, skill, motivation, job performance, navy, RMN

INTRODUCTION

According to Ostovar (2016) job performance are affected by the volume of expected behaviors towards certain assignments are dependent on the efforts and success of the employee's implementation which affects job performance. Najafi (2011) state job performance evaluation must be systematic and a disciplined assessment of people's work in relation to how they perform their task in entrusted jobs determines their possible for growth and improvement. Campbell & Wiernik (2015) distinguish between individual performance, outcome and its determinant that effect of everything else. Performance is something under control of the individual such as knowledge, skill and choice behavior in facilitates organization's goals. However, the outcome depends on external factor that beyond individual control such as sales, stock prices and salary. Job performance are purely related with human capital. Human capital relates to individual knowledge and ability that permits coaching in action and economic growth. The organization must influence the skill and capability of its employee by encouraging individual and organizational knowledge and generating a supportive environment where knowledge enhanced, shared and applied. Individual knowledge and ability can be thriving from various approaches. Formal training and education are among approaches or an instrument of human capital development.

The effectiveness of a training and education is measured to meet the requirement of job performance in peacetime responsibilities and war time. Most of the countries in the world nowadays have a very modern and advance military technology, which require a very strict demands in operating the system. The operator is highly required to have diverse skill levels, coupled with present fiscal constraints to operate in modern combat systems. Additionally, the requirement to achieve the objective requires a faster adaption towards it compared to recent history. Any single mistake will not be tolerated because it will affect the lives of the person on board as well as government properties. Individual performance will lead to high relevance for organizations, satisfaction of employee and better career development (Campbell & Wiernik, 2015).

As a young officer, one of the performances that they need to display are getting the certificates to be able to become Officer of the Watch (OOW). To get these certificates, they need to perform well in navigating the ship safely as well as understanding and applying the Rule of the Road. Besides, there is other thing that they need perform such as administration in harbor and becoming assistant to warfare director. Young officer had received a lot of training modules. The training program cover various subject that aims to enhance knowledge and build up skill to become competent executive officer on completion of the course. Training module include navigation practical, handling of small arm, communication class, warfare exposure as well as sea training on board selected ships. Besides that, training also emphasize in building motivation and confidence among young officers by presenting public speaking, organizing some events, and leadership class. Thus, the study objectives are:

- a. To examine the influence of knowledge (information processing, problem solving, specialization) towards job performance among RMN young officer.
 - i. To examine the influence of knowledge in information processing job performance among RMN young officer.
 - ii. To examine the influence of knowledge in problem-solving towards job performance among RMN young officer.

- iii. To examine the influence of knowledge specialization towards job performance among RMN young officer.
- b. To examine the influence of communication skill towards job performance among RMN young officer.
- c. To examine the influence of motivation towards job performance among RMN young officer.

Meanwhile the research questions are:

- a. Does knowledge (information processing, problem solving, specialization) have significant influence towards job performance among RMN young officer?
 - i. Does knowledge in information processing have significant influence towards job performance among RMN young officer?
 - ii. Does knowledge in problem solving have significant influence towards job performance among RMN young officer?
 - iii. Does knowledge specialization have significant influence towards job performance among RMN young officer?
- b. Does communication skill have significant influence towards job performance among RMN young officer?
- c. Does motivation have significant influence towards job performance among RMN young officer?

The scope of this research is to focus on the job performance of young officer onboard RMN ship. This young officers with the rank of Acting Sub Lieutenant and Sub Lieutenant are officers who just commissioned from Universiti Pertahanan Nasional Malaysia (UPNM) and completing training at KD Sultan Idris (KDSI) I for one year. They will serve onboard RMN ship and required to complete several tasks to get several certificates to become qualified seaman officer. Target population of this study is young officer from executive branch that had served with RMN less than five years either onboard ships or bases. Some view also will be gathered from senior officer that have experience as commanding officer or head of department in RMN ships. For this study, questionnaires and interview will become the techniques for data collection. The questionnaires will be given to the young officer while interview will be conducted on selected senior officers. All respondents are selected from officers in Lumut Naval Base, Perak.

LITERATURE

UNDERPINNING THEORY

Campbell Theory

Job performance relates to whether a person performs their own specific jobs well. According to Campbell (1990), a worker's performance is based on an individual level motivation. According to Campbell, a certain set of goals within a job can be determined its job performance by reaching the desired goals but not the definite significances of the acts achieved within a job. Campbell (1990) has suggested that declarative knowledge, motivation, procedural knowledge and skill are what determines the differences based on performance as in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Campbell Determinant of Job Performance
(Campbell, 1990)

Relationship between Self-Knowledge and Job Performance

Recent dissemination of service work and overflow of knowledge workers have particularly emphasized the importance of cognitive ability for handling working issues. Every organization must optimize the competencies of their employees by identify and create appropriate task for them. Organization must continuously build the future on the knowledge work such as information processing, problem solving and specialization to remain competitive in complex situation. Knowledge employees are assigned to handle specific jobs with a set of work characteristics. Knowledge characteristics give a huge impact on work outcomes. Knowledge characteristics are the structural features of jobs that affect the development and utilization of information and skills (Parker et al, 2001). If employees enrich with the knowledge, they can do challenging jobs, create the employee's creativity in problem solving, analyses complex information and utilize it (Morgeson & Humphrey, 2006). Demanding and complex work settings for knowledge workers should positively influence on their task and performance. This study is applicable to study the importance of knowledge in information processing, problem solving and specialization toward young officer performance.

Relationship between Communication Skill and Job Performance

Communication skill is the ability to communicate effectively and efficiently with others. Communication skill was significantly related to employee productivity. Organizational communication enables managers for the exchange of information within the organization. The role of communication skills is one of the most important roles as expressing work of managers that it is important to the success and effectiveness of them (Ashrafi, 2005). Farsi (2016) analyses the relationship between communication skill and employees' job performance. 155 people from Golestan's National Company shows the significant and positive relationship between communication skills toward job performance. This result is applicable for RMN situations where

communication is essential to build a cohesive and effective team, manage the performance of team members and minimize the risk.

Relationship between Motivation and Job Performance

The motivation will create a positive behavior inside employee's personality to meet desired goal. Employer can increase employees' job performance if they emphasize on maintaining employees' motivation such as acknowledging employees work and effort, providing a good working environment, considering their needs as well as pleasant job design. Elding, Tobias and Walker (2006) stated that a key task of management is that of motivating the organizations workforce to work more effectively towards its objectives. These motivations are popularly known like rewards, allowance, good working condition and others. Shahzadi, Javed, Pirzada, Nasreen, & Khanam (2014) study which extent motivation affects the Pakistan teachers' performance. Based on the result show significant and positive relationship exists between employee motivation and employee performance. In RMN, motivation like rewards, good conduct batch and appreciation are popularly given to perform employees. These factors encourage themselves and peer to give more effort to give best outcome. Hence, the proposed framework is as following figure:

Figure 2: Proposed Research Framework Model

Based on the empirical study, the hypotheses of the current study are:

H1a: There is a significant influence between knowledge in information processing and job performance.

H1b: There is a significant influence between of knowledge in problem-solving and job performance.

H1c: There is a significant influence between specialization knowledge and job performance.

H2: There is a significant influence between communication skill and job performance. H3: There is a significant influence between motivation and job performance.

METHODOLOGY

The current study selects all the previous five years young officers from 2013 until 2017 as the most appropriate to answer the questionnaires. They were selected because they have just completed the Executive Application Course (EAC) and still fresh with the program and able to provide answer in the sincere way possible to reflect the true situation. All young executive officers involve in this survey currently appointed as complement staff on board the ship or base. The respondents were from Lumut Naval Base and 127 sets of questionnaires survey were given out to young officers which consists of 45 statements from the five section demographics of personnel and items. The procedure of answering the question were briefed and given guidance to those taking the questionnaire. Two weeks were given to the respondents to complete the task. The questionnaires were distributed through link that generated from google form.

RESULTS

Table 1: Demographic profile

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex		
Male	119	93.7
Female	8	6.3
Race		
Malay	111	87.4
Chinese	0	0
Indian	11	3.9
Other	5	8.7
Marital Status		
Bachelor	101	79.5
Married	26	20.5
Rank		
Acting Sub Lieutenant	27	21.3
Sub Lieutenant	65	51.2
Lieutenant	35	27.6
Highest Education Qualification		
Degree	127	100
Current Appointment		
Ship	89	70.1
Base	38	29.9
Working Experience		
One Year	28	22.0
Two Years	34	26.8
Three Years	11	8.7
Four Years	54	42.5

From the table 1 above, the total of 127 respondents, 93.7% were males and 6.3% were females. These percentages possibly reflect the number of female staffs in the RMN. This is due to the policy of maintaining only 5% female in the service.

Table 2: Multiple linear regression analysis

Model	R Square	F Value	Standardized Coefficients Beta	T-Value	Sig
Regression	.516	25.799			.000*
Knowledge					
a) Information Processing			.104	1.060	.291
b) Problem Solving			.115	1.046	.297
c) Specialization			.560	5.937	.000*
Communication Skill			.090	1.184	.239
Motivation			-.205	-2.779	.006*

a. Dependent Variable: Job Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Knowledge, Communication Skill, Motivation

Table 2 above indicates that all independent variables together explained 51.6% (R square = .516) in young officer job performance, which is highly significant, as indicated by F-value of 25.79. Knowledge in information processing and problem-solving knowledge are not significant predictor of young officer job performance ($p=0.291$ and $p=0.297$, $p>0.05$). Specialization knowledge is significant predictor of young officers' job performance ($B=0.560$, $p<0.05$). However, when communication skill was also included in the regression equation, communication skill ($p=0.239$, $p>0.5$) became an insignificant predictor of young officer job performance and Beta standardized coefficient was reduced to 0.090. This suggests that communication skill support partially young officer job performance. When motivation is included, Beta standardized coefficient reduced to -0.205. An examination of the t-value indicated that specialization knowledge ($t=5.937$) contributed most to the young officer job performance followed by communication skill ($t=1.184$). Hence, specialization knowledge is the best predictor for young officer job performance.

Table 3: Result of Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	p-value	Decision
H1a: There is a significant influence between knowledge in information processing and job performance.	.291	Reject H1a
H1b: There is a significant influence between knowledge in problem solving and job performance.	.297	Reject H1b
H1c: There is a significant influence between specialization knowledge and job performance.	.000	Accept H1c
H2: There is a significant influence between communication skill and job performance.	.239	Reject H2
H3: There is a significant influence between motivation and job performance.	.006	Accept H3

CONCLUSION

This study has shown that specialization knowledge and motivation positively impact job performance. Finding of this study revealed that specialization knowledge played a more determinant role than another factor. Based on the research, some of the following recommendation and improvement should be considered to enhance the young officer job performance. Developing the program which regard to specific unit or ship. This program will provide knowledge for young officer to undergo specific class related to their assign unit or ship. This is to prepare them mentally and physically before reported to ship. Instead of team building course at Pusat Kepimpinan TLDM, few programs can be introduced such as practical application where all the young officers were given the responsibilities to organize the events, sharing session with Commanding Officer of ship or RMN higher echelon and workshop-oriented activities.

KDSI I must fully monitor the performance of young executive officer by asking for competency from ship six months after young officer reported to ship. Research involving the effectiveness of young officers on completion the course in RMN was rare. Few aspects that influenced job performance can be investigated for future research. Firstly, the research can be further improved

by expanding the time frame to give the researcher more time to do analysis. Secondly, other factors such as cognitive, physical, self-management and interpersonal skill can be used as other factors to determine job performance. Thirdly, future research could be expanded to technical and supply branch to determine the performance of young officer.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest regarding this manuscript.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

All authors are participants in the data collection and analysis and writing and revising the manuscript.

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